

Final PhD Thesis Report

ToxSauQMRA

Study of the tropism and persistence of *Toxoplasma gondii*: from pork carcass to sausage and dry ham, a quantitative risk assessment

Responsible OHEJP Partner: ANSES

Contributing OHEJP partners: RIVM

Contributing external partners: URCA, IFIP

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards.
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
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Duration	69 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

PhD Report	Final PhD Thesis Report Y5 (2022)
PhD Reference	PhDXX-domain code_ToxSauQMRA
PhD candidate	Filip Dámek
PhD Lead Supervisor	Radu Blaga (ANSES)
PhD second supervisor	Marieke Opsteegh (RIVM)
Other supervisor (s)	Pascal Boireau (ANSES), Joke van der Giessen (RIVM)
Due month of the deliverable	M66
Actual submission month	M66
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU <i>This is the default setting. This report will be entirely copied into One Health EJP Work Package 6 Deliverable D6.18 - Thesis Reports of up to 17 PhD studentships.</i>
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders / Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> WOAH <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>

INTRODUCTION

The final thesis or thesis report will be included in Deliverable 6.18 and the deadline to submit this deliverable to the European Commission is 30th June 2023. The deliverable will be a **public report** by default. **Where the final thesis report or final thesis contains information that must remain confidential under an embargoed period until the publications or outputs have been generated**, then a redacted version suitable for the public must be submitted.

A confidentiality clause should be included at the start of the redacted report or thesis clearly explaining any redactions, so the reader is aware. The embargo period should also be clearly stated.

- **PhDs that finish by 30th April 2023** are required to produce a drafted or final thesis as a final output. Once the PhD thesis is complete, PhD students should either submit an electronic version (PDF) of the thesis, or a DOI so that it can easily be linked (most theses are kept in a repository with open access unless by exception). The final thesis must be submitted to the WP6 team (wp6.onehealthjep@surrey.ac.uk) and uploaded to Zenodo by the PhD supervisor. In addition, the content covered in sections 1, 2, 7-16 of the thesis reporting template must also be completed and submitted to WP6 with the thesis and uploaded to Zenodo. Please ensure you upload the files in one Zenodo upload, so they have the same link.
- **PhD students that have not finished their PhD thesis by 30th April 2023** are required to produce a **Final Thesis Report** by completing the final thesis reporting template and to send a first version of the report back to the WP6 team (wp6.onehealthjep@surrey.ac.uk) **by 15th May 2023**.
- **In all cases**, PhD supervisors must submit the final (public) pdf(s) of the final PhD thesis to the WP6 team (wp6.onehealthjep@surrey.ac.uk) and **upload them to Zenodo by 30th June 2024**.

CONFIDENTIALITY

Where the final thesis report or final thesis contains information that must remain confidential under an embargoed period, then a redacted version suitable for the public must be submitted. The non-redacted final thesis (or a link to this document) must be emailed to the WP6 team when it is available.

A confidentiality clause should be included at the start of the report or thesis clearly explaining any redactions, so the reader is aware. The embargo period should also be clearly stated.

1. PhD Project team composition

PhD student: Filip Dámek

University at which the PhD is registered: University Paris-Est Créteil, France.

Lead PhD Supervisor: Radu Blaga, French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES), France.

Second Supervisor: Marieke Opsteegh, National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM), the Netherlands.

Other Supervisors: Pascal Boireau, French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES), France; Joke van der Giessen, National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM), the Netherlands.

Date for PhD thesis submission: 05/05/2023

2. Abstract

500 words, 1 page. Please summarise the main scientific results and pay particular attention to the impact the project may have for the One Health EJP and its stakeholders (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), and national ministries. This abstract may be used as a standalone communication piece, and therefore should be clear so it can be read as a separate entity if needed.

Within ToxSauQMRA project we explored various aspects of addressing issues in pork production and reducing the spread of toxoplasmosis through mpork and pork products. We successfully composed a comprehensive literature review of the most recent prevalence of *T. gondii* in selected European animal populations to develop a Bayesian statistical model that estimates age-specific seroprevalence for individual animal species, considering the effects of region, outdoor access, and sample matrix. The model and related resources were made publicly available to aid and standardize the conduct and reporting of future prevalence studies.

Furthermore, we investigated the potential effects of *T. gondii* genotype and stage on clinical response and tissue distribution in pigs, providing valuable insights into the epidemiology of *T. gondii* in pigs. The highest prevalence of the parasite was observed in shoulder muscles, with the highest parasite load observed in the uterus. Strain- and stage-related patterns were noted, and the infection with the type III isolate and tissue cysts resulted in significantly more positive tissues and higher parasite burden in tissue cyst-infected tissues. We have expanded on the previous findings by investigating the distribution of *T. gondii* in pig tissues after experimental infection, highlighting the importance of considering infection routes and genotype in the development of preventive strategies against *T. gondii*.

In the next step, we assessed the inactivation potential of salt, nitrites and nitrates on *T. gondii* in dry sausages and processed pork. We observed inactivation of the parasite in all tested recipes with salt concentrations above 2% after less than a day. In addition, we completed an assessment of the French and European country-specific meat products including their composition and processing steps during production that might influence viability of potential *T. gondii* tissue cysts within.

Finally, we adjusted and updated the necessary databases for the development of novel heating and salting models applicable to meat and meat products. Our goal was to incorporate these models into the final quantitative microbial risk assessment (QMRA) model, which aims to estimate the relative contribution of different sources of *T. gondii* human infection. This novel QMRA model will provide an effective tool for decision-makers in the development of preventive strategies against the parasite.

3. Introduction and Objectives

Please provide a detailed introduction which includes a literature review, followed by an explanation of the project objectives, and the realised or expected outcomes, impact and cross-sector collaborations.

- *Expected outcomes:*
 - *Have the results been implemented in your institute, consortium partners, elsewhere? Across sectors? Are such implementations planned? Has this been discussed at the level of One Health EJP partner organisations? What should be done to do so?*
- *Expected impact:*
 - *Scientific impact: Can new research be based on the outputs?*
 - *Societal and policy impact: If implemented at different institutes or organisations, what would that mean for animal health, public health, food safety, for preparedness at national and international levels. Can the results be useful for EU reference laboratories, international organisations, One Health EJP stakeholders etc.*

4. Materials and Methods

Option 1: Please provide details of the materials and methods used in as much detail as possible (consider this is a public report).

Option 2: If your materials and methods are part of a published scientific paper, please provide the DOI link to the scientific papers here instead.

5. Scientific Results and Discussion

Please provide your scientific results and discussion in this section and organise them into chapters (see below) which follow a clear 'storyline'. Describe all other aspects which contributed to the findings (e.g., integrative activities, collaborations etc.).

Please provide as much detail as possible (consider this is a public report) and include enough detail to understand the work done and outcomes (e.g. milestones, deliverables, outputs) of all Work Packages (e.g. WP1, WPN) and associated tasks (e.g. WP1 – T1, WPN – TN...).

a. Chapter 1: xxx

b. Chapter 2: xxx

c. Chapter N: xxx

6. Conclusions and Future work and perspectives

500 words, 1 page (Calibri or Arial Font size 11, margins of minimum 2cm). Please provide conclusions based on the work achieved, and any future recommended work.

7. PhD project self-evaluation

500 words, 1 page (Calibri or Arial Font size 11, margins of minimum 2cm). Please comment to what extent the initial PhD project objectives as laid out in the proposal have been met. Any deviation from the original project proposal should be included and justified.

We have diligently adhered to the original project proposal and have successfully executed a majority of the promised actions. However, there were certain parts of the project that required a prompt adaptation due to various reasons.

As part of the original project, dry sausages and dry hams were to be produced. The dry hams were meant to be manufactured by INRAe Corte (Corsica), utilizing two traditional salting techniques (a long one: 2.5 days/kg and a short one: 1 day/kg). Unfortunately, due to a local strike in the Marseille harbour, the hams were delayed by 10 days. This caused the sanitary quality of the meat to be questionable in terms of manufacturing. As a result, only the long salting technique was employed, and 300g of product was taken at D30 and D90 due to the Covid19 pandemic.

Furthermore, we had to face complications in the supply chain and shortages of chemicals required for qPCR due to the pandemic, which caused delays in the project timeline. However, despite the challenges, all predetermined milestones were successfully achieved, and the outcomes were valorized in the form of presentations at national and international congresses, as well as publications in peer-reviewed journals.

The QMRA model for French meat products will be an integral part of the final QMRA model, which will be the final outcome of the linked OH EJP Toxosources. Thanks to collaborations in these interconnected projects, we can ensure that the final deliverable will be of the highest quality, meeting all expectations.

8. Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

The following list refers to the deliverables and milestones as mentioned in the successive project Annual Work Plans. This part of the report should demonstrate that the project has delivered all that was planned.

Please verify, correct if required, complete, and ensure that all deliverables are uploaded - both on the private project group of the One Health EJP website and on Zenodo.

Note that all deliverables should be public by default. If a deliverable should be temporarily confidential, the justification should be mentioned in the Document Management section in the deliverable template, and the Deliverable Confidentiality Statement Form should be completed and submitted, which provide details of when the deliverable can be made public. It is the responsibility of the PhD supervisor to keep the WP6 team informed of any delays to making these deliverables public. In exceptional circumstances where confidentiality is required indefinitely, this should be clearly justified.

If applicable, please assign an integrative category (1 to 8) to each of the deliverables, as this helps PMT to assess possible impacts the outcome may have.

Deliverables

Please fill the table belows. If a delay is due to the COVID-19 crisis, please add a comment. if there are no corrections required then no action is necessary.

PhD reference	PhD Project deliverable number	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered (month)	Comments	Integrative categories*
PhDXX-domain code_ToxSauQMRA	D-PhD-ToxSauQMRA-WP3.2	Report on relative contribution of different meat products and tissues to human <i>T. gondii</i> infection.	M60	-	Delayed due to the involvement of key scientists in response to COVID-19 pandemic. Planned to achieve in M68.	

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

PhD reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Actual delivery date	Achieved	Comments
PhDXX-domain code_ToxSauQMRA	M-PhD-ToxSauQMRA-01	Processing parameters for relevant meat products are provided as input for QMRA.	M55	M54	Yes	Achieved ahead of schedule
PhDXX-domain code_ToxSauQMRA	M-PhD-ToxSauQMRA-02	Country-specific estimates for prevalence of human <i>T. gondii</i> infection provided as input data for QMRA	M57	M57	Yes	

9. Interactions with JRPs/JIPs or with external (global, EU, national or regional) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), national and international surveillance programmes.

Please describe any link (workshops, meetings, missions etc.) with a Joint Research Project or Joint Integrative Project.

In the current OH EJP ToxSauQMRA, we have successfully cooperated with the JRP Toxosources on several levels, ensuring smooth development of novel QMRA model, aiming to estimate the relative contribution of different sources of *T. gondii* human infection.

10. Interactions with OHEJP stakeholders

Please describe any link with any external (EU, national and international) relevant project (name + website), or with the One Health EJP [stakeholders](#).

All results achieved through work on this project were disseminated at national and international scientific meetings and congresses. This among other things provided us an opportunity to deepen our collaboration with colleagues on future projects.

Furthermore, this project was closely linked with OH EJP Toxosources, <https://onehealthejp.eu/projects/foodborne-zoonoses/jrp-toxosources>.

11. Added value and benefits during PhD resulting from being part of the OHEJP doctoral programme and consortium

Please describe here what you perceived as additional value as a result of your PhD being a part of the One Health EJP e.g. training, networking with other disciplines or countries and access to a wide range of expertise.

The One Health concept plays a crucial role in bridging individual fields of research, opening up new avenues to address existing research gaps and promoting creativity and innovative ideas that push the boundaries of scientific horizons. It was a privilege to share my research findings with like-minded professionals from other OH EJP projects, and the opportunity to engage in collaborative partnerships and network with peers was invaluable. The OH EJP meetings provided a unique platform for me to gain insights into diverse scientific perspectives that enriched my understanding of complex research topics beyond my own area of expertise.

In addition, the OH EJP consortium is a diverse and dynamic community of motivated and passionate scientists who are dedicated to advancing knowledge in their respective fields. The strength of this community lies in its collective ability to help troubleshoot individual setbacks and support each other in overcoming challenges. The power of this collaborative approach cannot be overstated, and I am grateful for the opportunity to be part of such a dynamic and supportive community that is working towards a common goal of improving public health through multidisciplinary research.

12. Transferrable skills and Training

Describe details of relevant transferrable skills, training courses or CPD training attended and undertaken by the PhD student throughout the PhD programme.

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Communications and Media Workshop: How Science Achievements Reach People and Contribute to a Better Life	Communication and Media	05-06/10/2020	University of Surrey, the United Kingdom; NDRVMI, BFSA, Bulgaria
Animal experimentation regulatory course - Designer	Animal experimentation	21/03-01/04/2022	Pasteur Institute, France
Statistiques et Langage R	Statistics	19/01-09/02/2021	University Paris-Est Créteil, France
Les Enjeux de la Bioéconomie	Bioeconomy	19-22/04/2021	Agreenium, France
Introduction to R	Language R	12/09/2022	DataCamp, online

13. Ethical Reviews

Please fill the table below. If there are no corrections required, then no action is necessary.

Comments of Ethics Advisors, January 2020	Comments PhD Project Supervisor, mid-2020	Comments of Ethics Advisors, October 2020

14. Scientific Publications

Please fill the table below.

Please make sure that all publications are listed. List peer-reviewed publications and others.

For every publication please specify:

- **Doi** reference
- Zenodo **link**
- Gold or green open access?
 - o If green: Length of the Embargo, if any. Open access to the publication must be ensured within a maximum of six months.

If no doi reference (e.g. article in journal, publication in conference proceedings or workshop, book or monograph, chapter in a book, thesis/dissertation, other), please provide as much information as possible.

Publication date	Publication title	Authors	DOI reference	Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? *please specify embargo length	Is it a Gold Open Access?
6.1.2023	Systematic Review and Modelling of Age-Dependent Prevalence of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> in Livestock, Wildlife and Felids in Europe		https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens12010097	https://zenodo.org/record/7515256#.Y7vzWXbMLIU	Yes	No	Yes

15. Additional Outputs

Other relevant dissemination outcomes can be highlighted here, e.g. non-scientific publications, proceedings, poster, video, tools, guidelines, patents, etc. If the outcome is a deliverable it should not be mentioned here.

Please indicate where the item can be found, for instance on Zenodo or any open access repository. Please indicate the link and check the functionality.

The results obtained within this project were presented in the form of oral presentations at international congresses and scientific meetings. In addition, the work was also disseminated through 15 poster presentations at 7 national and international scientific congresses.

16. Specific outcomes to highlight in dissemination and communications

In this paragraph you have the possibility to draw the attention to remarkable achievements that could be highlighted to illustrate the potential impact of your project.

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

Not at the moment.

Some of the outcomes of the project may already be in use or planned to be implemented in one or more partner institutes, or in external organisation (including stakeholders' organisations), or at the level of national authorities. Please describe.

17. One Health impact

About 500 words, 1 page – This part is extremely important, also for the One Health EJP stakeholders. Please, describe the impact of the PhD project, reflecting at least the following aspects:

- *Specify any direct or indirect impact the outcome of your project may have for international stakeholders active in the domains of foodborne zoonoses, AMR and/or emerging threats (ECDC, EFSA, FAO, WOA, WHO-EU; EU reference laboratories, etc.) e.g. suggested improvements of existing /planned surveillance programmes, new relevant databases for risk assessment updates, improved methodologies for risk assessment and management, etc.*
- *Please describe how regional or national authorities and stakeholders may implement and/or integrate any of the results from the project in their work. Which contacts, if any, have been taken between your consortium and authorities or stakeholders that may lead to such a knowledge transfer? Please describe.*
- *Has this project helped you building and strengthening the networking with other partners of the One Health EJP and beyond? Please describe shortly and give some examples.*

18. List of dissemination and communication activities

Please fill in one table per event you attended/organised during the entire life span of the project.
Please make sure they are registered online on the OneHealth EJP webpage:

<https://surveys.sciensano.be/index.php/754325?lang=en>

If relevant (for instance flyer, video, etc.) please include hyperlink.

Name of the activity:			
Date:			
Place:			
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			